

Platform Accountability in the Age of AI in India: Reconciling Corporate Autonomy with Digital Human Rights Under the UNGPS Framework

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Abstract

The rise of artificial intelligence (AI) in content moderation has transformed digital platforms into powerful gatekeepers of speech, capable of invisibilising dissent and curating information flows without transparency or accountability. In India, this transformation has coincided with an increasingly interventionist regulatory approach, particularly under the Information Technology Rules, 2021. This convergence has led to growing concerns over algorithmic suppression, opaque moderation practices, and the erosion of digital human rights, including freedom of speech and access to information. The central legal dilemma lies in reconciling the operational autonomy of private platforms with the constitutional and international obligations to protect users' rights in the digital realm.

This article critically evaluates India's current legal framework and its capacity to uphold platform accountability in the AI age. It explores the applicability of the United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs) as a normative blueprint for reform. Drawing on global regulatory models, the article recommends a hybrid approach integrating statutory mandates, soft law mechanisms, algorithmic audits, and independent oversight to ensure that India's digital governance is both innovation-friendly and rights-respecting.

Keywords

India, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Information Technology Rules, 2021, Digital Realm, United Nations Guiding Principles (UNGP).

Introduction

The evolution of artificial intelligence (AI) has transformed the operational logic of digital platforms such as Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), Instagram, and YouTube, where algorithmic systems now shape what content is seen, prioritised, or removed. These platforms operate as powerful intermediaries in the digital public sphere, enabling expression but also exercising significant control over visibility and narrative. [i] In India, this dynamic has been amplified by the rise of governmental content regulation under the Information Technology Act, 2000 and its accompanying rules, particularly the Information Technology (Intermediary Guidelines and Digital Media Ethics Code) Rules, 2021. [ii] However, the increasing use of opaque AI-driven moderation systems, combined with state influence over platform content decisions, has raised critical concerns about censorship, algorithmic suppression, and digital rights violations.

The dual tension at play involves, on the one hand, the autonomy of private platforms to design, implement, and enforce their own moderation policies, and on the other hand, the state's constitutional obligation to protect fundamental rights, including the right to freedom of speech under Article 19(1)(a) of the Indian Constitution and the right to privacy under Article 21. [iii] These tensions become particularly complex in the Indian context, where private actors are not traditionally held directly accountable for constitutional rights infringements, yet increasingly influence public discourse through automated tools of governance. [iv]

To navigate this space, international soft law frameworks most notably, the United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs) offer a normative roadmap for platform responsibility. The UNGPs articulate a tripartite framework: the state duty to protect human rights, the corporate responsibility to respect them, and the need for access to effective remedies. [v] While not binding, they have shaped both international human rights discourse and corporate governance standards, including in the digital and AI sectors.

This article interrogates the possibility of reconciling corporate autonomy with digital human rights in India through the lens of the UNGPs. It examines whether existing Indian laws sufficiently protect users' rights in the age of AI, and whether adopting UNGP-inspired norms can bridge the governance gap in a rapidly digitising democracy. The central research question is whether India can operationalise the principles of accountability, transparency, and due process in AI-based content moderation without undermining platform innovation or constitutional freedoms.

Algorithmic Suppression and Digital Gatekeeping in India

Digital platforms today act as gatekeepers of expression, using algorithmic tools not only to personalise content but also to rank, demote, flag, or delete user posts. In India, this has resulted in growing instances of algorithmic suppression a term referring to AI-driven invisibilisation or silencing of content without meaningful human oversight or accountability mechanisms. [vi] Unlike traditional censorship, which is overt and attributable to the state, algorithmic suppression is often covert, systemic, and justified by opaque platform policies or vague community guidelines. [vii]

This phenomenon raises critical questions in a constitutional democracy where access to information and the right to free speech are protected under Article 19(1)(a). During recent social and political events such as the farmers' protest (2020–21), the COVID-19 pandemic, and the anti-CAA protests platforms were either compelled by the state to restrict content or took voluntary action to demote hashtags and deplatform dissenting voices. [viii] Much of this moderation was carried out by automated systems without due process or the opportunity for meaningful appeal.

The problem is exacerbated by India's evolving regulatory framework. Under Section 69A of the Information Technology Act, 2000, the central government is empowered to direct intermediaries to block public access to information in the interest of sovereignty, security, or public order. [ix] These directions are issued in secrecy and are not subject to public review, creating a legal architecture that permits unaccountable censorship. The IT Rules, 2021, further extend the state's power by mandating platform compliance with takedown timelines and appointing grievance redressal officers, while imposing significant liability for non-compliance. [x] These obligations, coupled with AI-based content policing, risk transforming platforms into instruments of executive will, devoid of independence or user-oriented rights safeguards. Moreover, AI systems embedded in content moderation tools are neither neutral nor infallible. They often reflect training biases, linguistic and cultural limitations, and implicit assumptions that disproportionately impact marginalised users. For example, posts in regional Indian languages or on sensitive political topics are more likely to be erroneously flagged or suppressed. [xi] Without transparency in algorithm design, impact assessments, or public audits, the risks of systematic discrimination remain unaddressed.

Thus, algorithmic suppression, when combined with vague governmental directives and a lack of procedural safeguards, threatens the very foundation of digital human rights in India. It calls for a robust policy response that reconciles the legitimate interests of content moderation with the principles of accountability, transparency, and fundamental freedoms.

Corporate Autonomy vs. State Regulation: The Indian Legal Dilemma

At the heart of the discourse on platform accountability in India lies a fundamental legal dilemma: digital platforms, as private entities, enjoy a degree of operational autonomy, while the Indian State bears constitutional obligations to protect individual rights. This duality becomes especially complex in the context of content moderation powered by AI where platforms regulate speech, often beyond the scrutiny of constitutional safeguards traditionally applicable only to state action.

The Indian Constitution guarantees the right to freedom of speech and expression under Article 19(1)(a), subject to reasonable restrictions under Article 19(2). [xii] However, this right is enforceable only against the state or instrumentalities of the state, not against private actors. [xiii] As a result, users aggrieved by content removal, deplatforming, or shadow banning by social media platforms have limited constitutional remedies, unless state involvement or compulsion can be established.

Yet, the state is not a neutral bystander. Increasingly, it exerts regulatory pressure on platforms through laws such as the Information Technology Act, 2000, the IT Rules, 2021, and orders under Section 69A, which empower the government to require the takedown of content. [xiv] This has created a regime of indirect censorship, where platforms facing potential legal consequences become overzealous in content removal to ensure compliance, even in the absence of clear violations. This chilling effect undermines the autonomy of platforms while exposing users to arbitrary censorship.

Jurisprudence has struggled to keep pace with this regulatory evolution. In *Shreya Singhal v Union of India*, the Supreme Court struck down Section 66A of the IT Act for being vague and chilling free speech but upheld the constitutionality of Section 69A while mandating procedural safeguards. [xv] Despite this, the secrecy and opacity of takedown orders under Section 69A continue to be problematic, as no obligation exists to publicly disclose such directives or allow judicial review before implementation.

The doctrine of horizontal application of fundamental rights though evolving in comparative constitutional systems is nascent in India. While the Supreme Court has recognised certain fundamental rights as enforceable against private actors in contexts such as education and employment, [xvi] it has not yet extended this principle to the digital sphere. In *Faheema Shirin v State of Kerala*, the Kerala High Court acknowledged the right to access the internet as a part of Article 21 but stopped short of applying constitutional duties to private internet service providers or platforms. [xvii]

This legal vacuum necessitates a reimagining of regulatory frameworks that go beyond binary classifications of public and private actors. Given the quasi-public nature of large digital platforms, their control over digital discourse, and their algorithmic governance functions, it is imperative to evolve mechanisms that ensure accountability without eroding their operational independence. The UNGPs, by offering a middle path rooted in soft law obligations, may hold the key to reconciling this conflict.

The UNGPs Framework and Its Relevance to AI-Driven Platforms

The United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs), endorsed by the Human Rights Council in 2011, offer a globally recognised soft law framework that articulates the responsibility of business enterprises to respect human rights. [xviii] Although non-binding, the UNGPs have significantly shaped transnational discourse on corporate governance, particularly in sectors with wide social impact such as technology, data, and artificial intelligence (AI). For AI-driven digital platforms, the UNGPs are increasingly relevant, providing a normative baseline to ensure that their operations, including content moderation, do not infringe upon fundamental rights.

The UNGPs are structured around three foundational pillars:

1. The State Duty to Protect Human Rights
2. The Corporate Responsibility to Respect Human Rights
3. Access to Effective Remedies for Victims of Business-Related Abuses [xix]

Within the AI context, these principles acquire new dimensions. The state duty to protect implies not only legislating for rights protection but also ensuring that regulatory frameworks address the risks posed by AI algorithms, especially those deployed in public-influencing spaces like social media. In India, however, existing laws such as the IT Act, 2000 and the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023 fall short of embedding human rights safeguards into the design, deployment, and auditing of AI systems used by platforms. [xx]

The corporate responsibility to respect human rights requires platforms to conduct human rights due diligence across their operations including in the development and implementation of automated content moderation systems. [xxi] This includes assessing the impact of AI on freedom of expression, privacy, and non-discrimination; ensuring transparency in takedown decisions; and offering accessible mechanisms for appeal. In the Indian context, where platform decisions affect millions and often operate without clear procedural protections, implementing such responsibilities becomes critical.

International bodies such as the UN B-Tech Project and the OECD AI Principles have reinforced the need for algorithmic accountability through corporate due diligence and risk-based impact assessments. [xxii] These initiatives call on companies to be transparent about their AI tools, particularly in how algorithms moderate user-generated content or suppress information based on automated triggers.

Moreover, the access to remedy pillar of the UNGPs requires that both states and companies ensure the availability of grievance redressal mechanisms that are legitimate, accessible, equitable, transparent, and rights-compatible. [xxiii] While Indian law now mandates platforms to appoint grievance officers under the IT Rules, 2021, these mechanisms often lack independence, procedural clarity, and binding remedial power. A UNGPs-compliant model would require establishing independent oversight, user notification prior to content removal, and the opportunity for timely and meaningful appeals.

In sum, the UNGPs offer a roadmap for embedding ethical and rights-based governance into the AI-driven operations of platforms. Their application in India can serve to bridge the normative vacuum between corporate self-regulation and state-led enforcement, offering a hybrid model that respects autonomy while promoting accountability in the digital public sphere.

Bridging the Gap: Need for Indian Legislation or Soft Law Frameworks

India's current legal framework governing digital platforms is fragmented, reactive, and ill-equipped to address the nuanced challenges posed by AI-driven content governance. While laws like the Information Technology Act, 2000, and the recently enacted Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023, establish broad duties on platforms with regard to content moderation and data protection, they fail to embed a comprehensive rights-based accountability mechanism that aligns with international soft law principles such as the UNGPs. [xxiv] This regulatory vacuum necessitates the adoption of a hybrid model one that draws upon both legislative reform and soft law instruments to ensure platform responsibility, algorithmic transparency, and human rights compliance.

A key shortcoming of existing laws lies in their focus on procedural compliance rather than substantive rights protection. The IT Rules, 2021, for instance, mandate platforms to act on content removal requests within tight timelines and designate grievance officers. [xxv] However, they do not require platforms to conduct human rights impact assessments, publish transparency reports, or submit to independent audits of their algorithms and content moderation practices. These gaps allow both the state and corporations to escape accountability for decisions that shape public discourse and influence electoral or socio-political narratives.

Drawing upon the UNGPs, India should consider mandating mandatory algorithmic impact assessments (AIAs) for large platforms operating within its jurisdiction. These assessments should evaluate the effects of AI systems on free speech, privacy, non-discrimination, and access to information. A legal framework, either as part of a forthcoming Digital India Act or in the form of subordinate rules under the DPDP Act, could institutionalise such assessments in a structured and periodic manner. [xxvi] Additionally, there is a pressing need for public transparency obligations. Platforms must be legally bound to publish detailed transparency reports disclosing data on takedown requests, AI-driven moderation outcomes, shadow bans, and appeals processed. Such disclosures should be overseen by an independent body perhaps a Digital Platform Accountability Commission modelled on the UK's Online Safety Regulator or the EU's Digital Services Coordinator. [xxvii] These institutions could operate under a quasi-judicial mandate to resolve user grievances and monitor platform compliance with ethical AI and digital rights standards. A promising step would be the adoption of a Code of Practice on Algorithmic Governance, developed through a multi-stakeholder process involving civil society, academia, technologists, and platforms. While not legally binding, such a code guided by the UNGPs could help fill normative gaps and foster a culture of self-regulation aligned with human rights. The Advertising Standards Council of India (ASCI) and Self-Regulatory Organisation (SRO) models from financial regulation could serve as institutional analogues. Ultimately, reconciling platform autonomy with public accountability in the Indian digital ecosystem requires a layered approach. Statutory mandates can define minimum thresholds for rights compliance, while soft law tools can offer flexibility and adaptability in regulating emerging technologies. The UNGPs, with their emphasis on corporate due diligence and state responsibility, offer the scaffolding to build this equilibrium.

Case Studies and Comparative Insights

To design a responsive legal and ethical regime for AI-based platform governance in India, it is instructive to study how other jurisdictions are addressing similar challenges. Countries across Europe and the UK, in particular, have enacted or proposed comprehensive regulatory frameworks that integrate platform accountability, algorithmic transparency, and user rights into statutory obligations. These models reflect varying degrees of reliance on hard law, co-regulation, and soft law principles that align closely with the UNGPs. A comparative study reveals key lessons for India in balancing corporate autonomy and human rights protection in the digital age.

European Union: The Digital Services Act (DSA)

The European Union's Digital Services Act (DSA), adopted in 2022, represents the most ambitious legal regime for regulating digital platforms and their algorithmic practices. [xxviii] It imposes tiered obligations based on the size and reach of platforms, with Very Large Online Platforms (VLOPs) subject to rigorous duties including algorithmic auditing, human rights impact assessments, transparency disclosures, and independent oversight by Digital Services Coordinators. [xxix] The DSA embodies the UNGPs' principles by requiring companies to respect users' rights through due diligence, and it mandates effective redress mechanisms for unjustified content removals. The DSA's structured approach to risk-based regulation, use of transparency reports, and provisions for systemic impact assessments can inform India's future legal architecture. In particular, India can adopt similar models to assess the social and democratic risks posed by algorithmic suppression on platforms with substantial reach and influence.

Germany: NetzDG and Its Amendments

Germany's Network Enforcement Act (NetzDG), enacted in 2017, requires large social media companies to remove "manifestly unlawful" content within 24 hours of notification or face heavy penalties. [xxx] Although it has been criticised for incentivising over-censorship and lacking procedural fairness, recent amendments have introduced user appeal rights and greater transparency obligations.

Germany has also supported algorithmic transparency initiatives, requiring companies to explain how their content curation systems work, especially in the context of harmful speech. The Indian IT Rules, 2021, which require expeditious takedown and designate grievance officers, are often likened to NetzDG. However, India lacks the statutory safeguards introduced in Germany to ensure user redressal, transparency in removals, and appeal mechanisms. Lessons from NetzDG suggest that procedural rights and independent oversight must accompany fast-track content regulation.

United Kingdom: Online Safety Act

The UK's Online Safety Act (OSA), enacted in 2023, empowers Ofcom, the communications regulator, to enforce platform accountability for harmful online content. [xxxi] It mandates that major platforms perform risk assessments regarding harmful content (including misinformation, cyberbullying, and algorithmic amplification of extremism), submit compliance reports, and adopt proportionate mitigation measures. The OSA also encourages safety by design, urging platforms to consider human rights at the design stage of algorithmic systems. Of particular relevance to India is the OSA's emphasis on design-stage intervention, which aligns with the UNGPs' call for early due diligence and risk prevention. India can incorporate such an approach in its proposed Digital India Act, mandating algorithmic design reviews, particularly in content-sensitive sectors.

Global Initiatives: The Santa Clara Principles and the Oversight Board

Beyond statutory frameworks, global civil society and platform-led initiatives have emerged to promote ethical governance. The Santa Clara Principles on Transparency and Accountability in Content Moderation, developed by a coalition of civil society groups, urge platforms to publish detailed rules, provide notice to users, and allow appeals against content decisions. [xxxii] Meta's Oversight Board, although company-funded, represents a form of institutionalised platform accountability that blends corporate self-regulation with quasi-judicial review. [xxxiii] India lacks any such self-regulatory architecture embedded in platform governance. Adapting these principles into a soft law or co-regulatory framework perhaps through a national charter of digital rights or a multi-stakeholder code could offer a practical middle path between state control and laissez-faire corporate policies.

Conclusion

As India embraces its digital future, the tension between corporate autonomy and the safeguarding of digital human rights has become increasingly pronounced. Platforms now play a quasi-public role in regulating speech, shaping discourse, and determining the boundaries of permissible expression all through automated systems that are opaque, unaccountable, and often biased. The rise of AI in content moderation has deepened these challenges, transforming the once-neutral role of platforms into active arbiters of public discourse. Yet, the legal framework in India has not evolved at the same pace. While recent laws like the IT Rules, 2021 and the DPDP Act, 2023 signal a regulatory intent, they fall short of embedding fundamental rights protections into the operational fabric of AI-based decision-making. Moreover, the constitutional doctrine in India does not currently impose positive obligations on private platforms to uphold digital rights, thereby creating a governance vacuum.

It is here that the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights offer a valuable normative compass. By articulating the shared responsibilities of states and corporations in protecting, respecting, and remedying human rights violations, the UNGPs provide a framework through which India can develop both legislative and institutional responses. Drawing from global models such as the EU's Digital Services Act, the UK's Online Safety Act, and initiatives like the Santa Clara Principles, India can chart a path that is locally rooted but globally aligned.

Ultimately, the goal is not to curtail platform innovation or dismantle their autonomy, but to ensure that the digital ecosystem operates within a rights-respecting architecture. A future-ready India must adopt a hybrid model anchored in statutory obligations, complemented by soft law tools, and supported by independent oversight that reconciles corporate freedom with the imperatives of constitutional democracy.

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